

IMIDOCHLORIDES. PART VIII. REACTION OF ANILIDE IMIDOCHLORIDES WITH ETHYL SODIOMALONATE. SYNTHESIS OF SOME 4-HYDROXY-2-ARYL-3-CARBETHOXYQUINOLINES

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In extension of the previous work of Shah and Heeramanek (*J. Chem Soc*, 1936, 428; 1937, 867) ethyl sodiomalonate has been condensed with various anilide imidochlorides containing substituents in the acid part of the molecule. The crude condensation products have been cyclised by heating under reduced pressure to the corresponding 4-hydroxy-2-aryl-3-carbethoxyquinolines, and the latter then hydrolysed to the corresponding carboxylic acids.

Just condensed equimolecular proportions of benzanilide imidochloride with ethyl sodiomalonate in ether and isolated (i) mono- α -phenyliminobenzylmalonic acid diethyl ester (I, R=Ph) and (ii) di- α -phenyliminobenzylmalonic acid diethyl ester (II). He also observed that the mono-condensation product (I, R=Ph) underwent cyclisation on heating at higher temperatures affording 4-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-carbethoxyquinoline (III, R=Ph; R₁=Et). He extended the above reaction to benz-*o*- and -*p*-toluidide imidochlorides and α - and β -naphthalide imidochlorides (Just, *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 2623; 1886, 19, 983, 1462, 1541).

Shah and Heeramanek modified the above method by carrying out the condensation in dry toluene and employing one additional mole of free ethyl malonate, thereby minimising the formation of the di-condensation product and improving the yield of the mono-condensation product and consequently that of the quinoline. They have applied the above modified method to the condensation of various substituted anilide imidochlorides and also to the imidochlorides derived from benzoyl derivatives of α - and β -naphthylamines, and have shown this synthesis to be of general applicability (Shah and Heeramanek, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 428; 1937, 867). Elderfield and co-workers have also applied this modified method for the synthesis of some substituted 4-hydroxy-2-phenylquinolines from the corresponding imidochlorides (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1272).

In extension of the work of Shah and Heeramanek (*loc. cit.*) ethyl sodiomalonate has been successfully condensed with anilide imidochlorides substituted in the acid part of the molecule. The imidochlorides employed in the present investigation were derived from *o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluic acids, *m*- and *p*-bromobenzoic acids, *p*-methoxybenzoic acid and β -naphthoic acid.

Except in the case of β -naphthanilide imidochloride, the intermediate condensation products could not be crystallised and the crude products were directly cyclised when 4-hydroxy-2-aryl-3-carbethoxyquinolines (III, R=aryl; R₁=Et) with various substituents in the 2-phenyl ring were obtained, which are new. The condensation of β -naphthanilide imidochloride with ethyl sodiomalonate afforded crystallisable intermediate condensation product, which on cyclisation gave 4-hydroxy-2- β -naphthyl-3-carbethoxyquinoline (III, R= β -naphthyl; R₁=Et). All the 3-carbethoxyquinolines, obtained as above, on hydrolysis gave the corresponding quinoline-3-carboxylic acids (III, R=aryl; R₁=H).

The results of the present work have further shown the general applicability of the synthesis and that the presence of substituents in the acid part of the imidochloride molecule does not seem to appreciably effect either its condensation with ethyl sodiomalonate or the cyclisation of the condensation product to the quinoline derivative.

Shah and Heeramanek (*loc. cit.*) carried out the cyclisation of the intermediate condensation products by heating them above 180° (under atmospheric pressure), but in the present work it has been observed that the same could be effected more smoothly by treating them at 160°-170° under reduced pressure.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anilides required for the purpose were prepared by the method recommended by Shah and Deshpande (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1933, 2, II, 126).

o-Toluanilide imidochloride was prepared by heating *o*-toluanilide (10 g.) and phosphorus pentachloride (14 g.) till the evolution of fumes of hydrochloric acid ceased. It distilled at 160°-170°/10 mm., m.p. 36°, yield 5 g. (Found: Cl, 14.9. C₁₄H₁₂NCI requires Cl, 15.5 per cent).

Condensation of o-Toluanilide Imidochloride with Ethyl Sodiomalonate: 4-Hydroxy-2-o-tolyl-3-carbethoxyquinoline.—*o*-Toluanilide imidochloride (5 g., 1 mol.) was refluxed with ethyl sodiomalonate, prepared from ethyl malonate (10 g., 2 mol.) and sodium (0.6 g., 1 atom), in dry toluene at 130°-140° for 2 hours. The cooled reaction mixture was then treated with water and extracted with ether. Ether was distilled out under atmospheric pressure, and the toluene and excess of ethyl malonate were removed under reduced pressure. The crude condensation product so obtained could not be crystallised and was heated for cyclisation at 150°-160° under reduced pressure till the evolution of bubbles of ethyl alcohol ceased. The reaction mixture was then treated with cold alcohol when the quinoline derivative was obtained in crystalline form. It was recrystallised from hot alcohol, m. p. 184-86°, yield 2 g. (Found: N, 4.1. C₁₆H₁₇O₃N requires N, 4.6 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-o-tolylquinoline-3-carboxylic Acid.—The ethyl ester obtained as above was hydrolysed by refluxing with alcoholic sodium hydroxide for 2 hours. The acid obtained on acidification with hydrochloric acid was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 198°-200° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.5. C₁₇H₁₅O₃N requires N, 5.0 per cent).

The following compounds were prepared by the method described above. All the esters were crystallised from alcohol, whereas the corresponding acids were crystallised from acetic acid unless otherwise mentioned. The percentage yields of the quinolines are calculated on the weight of the imidochlorides employed.

m-Toluanilide imidochloride, prepared from *m*-toluanilide (10 g.) and phosphorus pentachloride (14 g.), distilled at 210° - $220^{\circ}/33$ mm., m.p. 37° . (Found: Cl, 15.0. $C_{14}H_{12}NCl$ requires Cl, 15.5 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-m-tolyl-3-carbethoxyquinoline was obtained from *m*-toluanilide imidochloride, m.p. 175 - 77° , yield 19%. (Found: N, 4.5. $C_{19}H_{17}O_3N$ requires N, 4.6 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-m-tolylquinoline-3-carboxylic acid, m.p. 183 - 86° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.9. $C_{17}H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 5.0 per cent).

p-Toluanilide imidochloride was prepared from *p*-toluanilide (14 g.) and phosphorus pentachloride (19 g.), yield 10 g. It distilled at $200^{\circ}/16$ mm. and had m.p. 45° . (Found: Cl, 15.2. $C_{14}H_{12}NCl$ requires Cl, 15.5 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-p-tolyl-3-carbethoxyquinoline was prepared from *p*-toluanilide imidochloride, yield 9%, m.p. 233 - 35° . (Found: N, 4.0. $C_{19}H_{17}O_3N$ requires N, 4.6 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-p-tolylquinoline-3-carboxylic acid, m.p. 273 - 75° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.5. $C_{17}H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 5.0 per cent).

m-Bromobenzanilide imidochloride was prepared from *m*-bromobenzanilide (14 g.) and phosphorus pentachloride (14 g.), b.p. 230 - $240^{\circ}/50$ mm., m.p. 39° . (Found: Halogen, 39.0. $C_{13}H_9NClBr$ requires halogen, 39.2 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-m-bromophenyl-3-carbethoxyquinoline was prepared from *m*-bromobenzanilide imidochloride, m.p. 231 - 33° . (Found: Br, 20.7. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3NBr$ requires Br, 21.5 per cent).

3-Hydroxy-2-m-bromophenylquinoline-3-carboxylic acid, m.p. 238° - 40° (decomp.). (Found: Br, 22.9. $C_{16}H_{10}O_3NBr$ requires Br, 23.2 per cent).

p-Bromobenzanilide imidochloride was prepared by Shah and Chaubal's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 652), m.p. 85 - 86° . Wheeler and Johnson (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1903, 30, 24;) give m.p. 78° .

4-Hydroxy-2-p-bromophenyl-3-carbethoxyquinoline from *p*-bromobenzanilide imidochloride (yield 24%), m. p. 258 - 60° . (Found: Br, 21.1. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3NBr$ requires Br, 21.5 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-p-bromophenylquinoline-3-carboxylic acid, m. p. 277° - 80° (decomp.). (Found: Br, 22.5. $C_{16}H_{10}O_3NBr$ requires Br, 23.2 per cent).

p-Methoxybenzanilide imidochloride distilled at $212^{\circ}/11$ mm. (Found: Cl, 13.9. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{13}ONCl$: Cl, 14.4 per cent). Wheeler and Johnson (*loc. cit.*) give m.p. 70° .

4-Hydroxy-2-p-methoxyphenyl-3-carbethoxyquinoline was prepared from p-methoxybenzanilide imidochloride, yield 28%, m.p. 216-20°. (Found: N, 4.0 C₁₉H₁₇O₄N requires N, 4.3 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-p-methoxyphenylquinoline-3-carboxylic acid, m.p. 226°-29° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.0. C₁₇H₁₇O₄N requires N, 4.7 per cent).

α -[Phenylimino-(β -naphthylmethyl)] malonic Acid Diethyl Ester.—The condensation of β -naphthanilide imidochloride (Shah and Chaubal, *loc. cit.*) and ethyl sodiomalonnate afforded the above as a pasty mass after usual treatment. It was left in a frigidaire for few days after which it solidified to a whitish mass. It was washed with petroleum ether, and after crystallisation from alcohol it gave a white solid, m.p. 150-52° (Found: N, 3.9. C₂₄H₂₃O₄N requires N, 3.6 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2- β -naphthyl-3-carbethoxyquinoline was prepared from the above, m.p. 227-30°. (Found: N, 3.6. C₂₂H₁₇O₃N requires N, 4.1 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2- β -naphthylquinoline-3-carboxylic acid, m. p. 238-40° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.1. C₂₀H₁₃O₃N requires N, 4.4 per cent).

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ERRATA

In part VII of the paper published in the March issue of this Journal (1949) please

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122	19	(III)	for (II)
123	1	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	,, - C ₁₈ N ₁₆ O ₂ N